

Time-resolved cryo-EM of G protein activation by a GPCR

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Molecular dynamics (MD) trajectories of all simulation data used in the publication can be 3D visualized in the browser in the following link:

- https://proteinformatics.uni-leipzig.de/mdsrv.html?load=file://_b2AR-complex-GTP/all-traj.js